

Moving to e-Consent

A first exploration of requirements and basic guidelines

Wilma

Data steward
Faculty Social Sciences

Responsible informed
consent workflow

Consent forms

Wilma

Ethical committee
Most non-WMO, some
WMO

Privacy department

Paper workflow

Huge amount
PDF variants

Various languages

Audio-Video-Photo

Personal data or not

Various age groups

Etc.

Online or lab

Incidental findings or not

Variants of reward

Variants
participants'
insurance

Loss consent
forms

Data breach

Force researchers to hand in
Storage 10/15 years
Huge paper archive

eConsent

How would the consent workflow look like?

What would be the content?

Can all research move to eConsent?

How would I present the information and questions?

How would I create the forms?

What are the requirements for the archive?

Which act of consent is sufficient?

Moving to eConsent

Exploration basic requirements and guidelines

LEGAL CONSIDERATIONS NON-WMO RESEARCH

- No legal prerequisite for identification of participant. Only proof of consent must be recorded.
 - Researcher responsible for recording process and proof of consent pursuant to GDPR
 - Not possible to develop a national procedure or method.
- Differences between research disciplines and institutes require customization.

FORM GENERATION

- Based on building blocks, which are maintained by back-office (data management/ethical department).
- Researcher fills out details of experiment by making predefined choices, based on building blocks of consent and adding free text. As a result aligned consent form is generated

Higher efficiency

- Changes are implemented in the building blocks and not in complete forms with various versions. Easier to update and comply with changing demands society or law/guidelines.
- Less prone to errors and more uniformity within in your institute

BUILDING BLOCKS INFORMED CONSENT

- Introduction and general information (department, ethical review, insurance)
- Purpose and background of the study
- What participation involves
- Advantages and disadvantages, including possible side-effects
- Participation rights
- Use and storage of your data
- (No) Compensation for participation
- Contact details for questions / feedback
- Signing of informed consent form

See also (ccmo)

HOW TO OFFER INFORMATION

- In bits and pieces. Participant has to scroll through each page
- Using animations
- Participant provides consent through conscious act. For example, checkmark and time stamp for general consent; actual typing for providing consent sensitive data.
- Get advice from Communication department
- Learn from other domains, e.g. developmental research, government, health care
- A good service would be to offer a portal (cf patient portals) presenting overviews of the information of the research to which the participant consented.

WORKFLOW

ARCHIVE

- 'Archiving by design' at the start of moving to eConsent with archive service
- Applicable storage term. Retention period is determined on a case-by-case basis (domain specific terms, importance of re-use, personal data) for more guidance see here.
- Project metadata assures cross referencing between the archived research data and the archived consent
- Ensure reliable archiving (forms cannot be changed, only authorized access)
- Destroy after end storage term by archive service
- Regular check (at least annually) on data sets

EXAMPLES ON PAPER

- UMC Utrecht
- Radboud University Nijmegen, Donders Centre for Cognition
- VU

EXAMPLES E-CONSENT

- IQVIA
- Janssen
- Dariah Eldah consent form wizard
- VU Zilver
- eConsent ouders/voogden RUG

Which act of consent is sufficient?

- No legal prerequisite for identification of participant. Only proof of consent must be recorded.
- Researcher responsible for recording process and proof of consent pursuant to GDPR (voluntary, specific, informed and unambiguous consent).
- Prerequisite for degree of identification not specified by law, but possibly determined by research-specific ethical codes of conduct, institute or researcher.
- Not possible to develop a national procedure or method. Differences between research disciplines and institutes require customization.

The GDPR does not prescribe to identify the participant. Consent could be provided by a check mark.

Action Point: Check further info and check within my institution which degree of identification applies

How would I create the forms?

Digital form generator:

- Based on building blocks, which are maintained by back-office (data management/ethical department)
- Researcher fills out details of experiment predefined choices
- Based on building blocks of consent and adding free text
- Result: aligned consent form

Higher efficiency

- Changes are implemented in the building blocks and not in complete forms with various versions. Easier to update and comply with changing demands society or law/guidelines.
- Less prone to errors and more uniformity within in your institute

I would need a user interface in which researchers can fill out the details of their experiments. On top of that I need a site on which the texts of consent are placed and maintained
Action Point: Contact ICT department

What would be the content or building blocks of the consent forms?

- Introduction and general information (department, ethical review, insurance)
- Purpose and background of the study
- What participation involves
- Advantages and disadvantages, including possible side-effects
- Participation rights – what if I do not want to participate or would like to stop during the study
- Use and storage of your data (and body material) – confidentiality, access, retention period, retraction of data, sharing of data, information DPA, special categories of data)
- (NO) Compensation for participation
- Contact details for questions / feedback (including independent person)
- Signing of informed consent form

Create texts for building blocks, attune with ethical committee and privacy department and provide these to ICT

How would I present the information and questions?

- In bits and pieces. Participant has to scroll through each page
- Using animations
- Participant provides consent through conscious act. For example, checkmark and timestamp for general consent; actual typing for providing consent sensitive data.
- Get advice from Communication department
- Learn from other domains, e.g. developmental, research, government, health care
- A good service would be to offer a portal (cf patient portals) presenting overviews of the information of the research to which the participant consented.

Contact communication department

What are the requirements for the archive?

- 'Archiving by design' at the start of moving to eConsent with archive service
- Applicable storage term. Retention period is determined on a case-by-case basis (domain-specific terms, importance of re-use, personal data).
- Project metadata cross-referencing between the archived research data and the archived consent
- Ensure reliable archiving: forms cannot be changed, only authorized access)
- Destroy after end storage term by archive service
- Regular check (at least annually) on data sets

Involve archiving department and ask them to help with these prerequisites

Example Radboud University, Faculty Social of Sciences

Custom made

Committee data stewards, privacy officer, ethical committee, technical support department and researchers

Example Radboud University, Faculty of Social Sciences

Form generator researchers

Reimbursement

Monetary reward

SONA credit

Potential incidental findings

Potential findings:

Privacy:

Personal data administrative

Sona Prolific Birthdate Name Address
This is independent from age and for administrative purposes only

Data admin optional:

Radboud University

DONDERS
INSTITUTE

Landelijk Coördinatiepunt
Research Data Management

Example Radboud University Faculty of Social Sciences

Potential findings, no action:

De verkregen onderzoeksgegevens zullen niet vanuit een medisch en/of klinisch perspectief worden bekeken. Uw deelname aan het onderzoek kan dan ook niet worden gezien als een medische/klinische test. Omdat het huidige onderzoek volledig anoniem is, kunnen eventuele scores die zorgwekkend zijn en/of die van persoonlijk klinisch belang kunnen zijn, niet teruggekoppeld worden. Als u zich naar aanleiding van de vragen zorgen maakt over uw gezondheid, dan adviseren wij u contact op te nemen met uw huisarts / de studentenpsycholoog / [specificeer]."

Building blocks offered/maintained by backoffice

Potential findings, active action:

De verkregen onderzoeksgegevens zullen niet vanuit een medisch en/of klinisch perspectief worden bekeken. Uw deelname aan het onderzoek kan dan ook niet worden gezien als een medische/klinische test. In uitzonderlijke gevallen kunnen er wel nieuwe gegevens worden verkregen betreffende uw gezondheidstoestand. U moet hierbij denken aan scores die zorgwekkend zijn en/of die van persoonlijk klinisch belang kunnen zijn. In dergelijke gevallen zult u hierover door de onderzoeker / een onafhankelijke expert [specificeer] geïnformeerd worden, maximaal 1 maand na deelname aan het onderzoek. Als u hierover niet geïnformeerd wenst te worden, kunt u niet aan het onderzoek deelnemen

No potential findings:

De verkregen onderzoeksgegevens zullen niet vanuit een medisch en/of klinisch perspectief worden bekeken. Uw deelname aan het onderzoek kan dan ook niet worden gezien als een medische/klinische test.

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Example Radboud University, Faculty Social of Sciences

Maintained by archiving department

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Questions?

Members of the committee 'moving to eConsent':

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Yeah, with these guidelines I have an idea on where to get started for implementing eConsent;)

Local considerations – why would you need identification?

Why would you need identification?

1. To retain proof that a specific person gave prior consent and to adhere to the right to be forgotten in the future.
2. Prerequisite of code of conduct or local institution.
3. To verify that a person has the identity he or she claims to have.
4. To ensure it concerns a unique person that only participates once.
5. To ensure it concerns a person.

Possible methods e.g., iDIN, ReadID, IRMA, Participant Identification Code (i.e. hash/checksum), video/audio connection, query/response procedure via Authenticator app, e-mail with unique one-time link to online survey, participant recruitment platforms (e.g., via Prolific ID), captcha, ...

- Request to verify identification documentation (e.g., passport) allowed, but participant not required to comply.
- Making a copy of identification documentation or recording social security number not allowed.
- For any identification method, (long-term) retention of name, identification number or any other identifiable personal data should be avoided.
 - E.g., using a hash/checksum to verify that you're dealing with the exact same person who originally gave consent, without storing any identifiable personal data for the long-term.

